

A solution to the water scarcity problem on the Mediterranean countries: HYDROUSA, closing the loops.

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ABSTRACT

Overpopulation and climate change can contribute to put water scarcity on the spotlight as one of the main global problem nowadays and in the future. Although it is a worldwide problem, some of the most affected places are the Mediterranean coast countries. Therefore, the development of new strategies to obtain freshwater from non-conventional sources is increasingly required. The European project HYDROUSA aims at evaluating innovative, regenerative and circular solutions for nature-based water management of Mediterranean coastal areas, closing water loops; nutrient management, boosting the agricultural profile; based on circular value chains.

HYDROUSA considers different non-conventional water sources (like greywater, rainwater, seawater, etc.) as well as conventional ones (treated urban wastewater) to obtain freshwater. However, micropollutants are not completely removed by the conventional wastewater treatment technologies. Since these substances, can have consequences for the environment or humans even at low concentrations, water reuse activities should be carefully evaluated. Thus, it is very important to track them through the water cycle and determine their source as well as removal efficiency and fate. Among emerging pollutants, antibiotics are pointed out as one the most worrisome. These substances are used to stop the growth of bacteria in an organism, but a continuous exposure to them can generate the spread of antibiotic resistance in microbiota. Actually, some antibiotics are included in the EU Watch List 2018/840, among other organic micropollutants such as hormones, neonicotinoid and carbamate pesticides, etc.

Therefore, it is of vital importance to elaborate comprehensive analytical methods capable of detecting and quantifying micropollutants even at concentrations of ng/L. One of ICRA task in HYDROUSA is to develop methodologies to monitor the presence of these compounds in source and treated water used for water reuse. This way we will also be able to evaluate the most efficient water treatment train to be applied in three Greek islands, in terms of removal of micropollutants. These methods will aim to simplify the existing analytical procedures.

Furthermore, an important fraction of the reclaimed water produced in the project will be used to irrigate crops. Thus, methods of extraction will also be developed to analyse the possible micropollutants that could leak/uptake into cultivated crops and vegetables.

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